

Procedure for the management and follow-up of TNA applications, including the manuals how to use the online submission and selection tool

Deliverable 1.1

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TABLE OF CONTENT

I.	Introduction.....	4
II.	Procedural manual.....	4
	A. How to access.....	4
	B. Structure	4
	1. Introduction.....	4
	2. Transnational access.....	4
	3. Eligibility conditions.....	4
	4. TNA process.....	4
	5. Application procedure	4
	6. Selection procedure.....	4
	7. Reporting procedure	4
	8. Valorization procedure	4
	9. Reimbursement procedure.....	4
	10. Support.....	4
	11. Agreement.....	4
	12. Forms.....	4
	13. Data protection notice.....	4
III.	Online submission and selection tool	4
	A. How to access.....	4
	B. Structure	4
	1. Login	5
	2. Homepage	5
	3. Submitting first stage application	5
	4. Submitting second stage application	8
	5. Evaluation of first/second stage applications	8
	6. Follow up of selection procedure	8
	7. Submitting start/interim/final reports.....	8
	8. Submitting follow-up questionnaire	8
	9. Submitting reimbursement claim	8
IV.	Conclusion	8
V.	Annexes	9
	A. Procedural manual	9
	B. First stage application	9
	C. Second stage application.....	9

PIGWEB

D. First stage selection.....	9
E. Second stage selection	9
F. Start report.....	9
G. Interim report.....	9
H. Final report.....	9
I. Follow-up questionnaire	9
J. Reimbursement claim	9

I. Introduction

The transnational access (TNA) program of the PIGWEB project allows external teams to access the partners' infrastructures. To ensure a transparent and efficient access, a procedural manual was written and an online submission and selection tool was designed:

- The procedural manual establishes all the guidelines regarding the eligibility to apply, the preparation, submission and evaluation of proposals, the submission of progress reports, the valorization of trial results, the reimbursement of any travel and subsistence costs and general support. This manual will therefore serve as a reference point for TNA applicants, TNA providers and the TNA management team throughout the entire TNA process.
- The online submission and selection tool allows interested parties to submit their applications easily and efficiently. In addition, the applicant will be able to follow up on his submission throughout the entire selection procedure.

II. Procedural manual

A. How to access

The procedural manual, including all associated forms (application, reporting, questionnaire and reimbursement), is accessible via the PIGWEB project website, through the following URL: (<https://www.pigweb.eu/tna-calls>).

B. Structure

The procedural manual consists of different sections and is added to this deliverable as Annex A.

1. Introduction
2. Transnational access
3. Eligibility conditions
4. TNA process
5. Application procedure
6. Selection procedure
7. Reporting procedure
8. Valorization procedure
9. Reimbursement procedure
10. Support
11. Agreement
12. Forms
13. Data protection notice

III. Online submission and selection tool

A. How to access

The online submission and evaluation tool is accessible via the PIGWEB project website, through the following URL: (<https://www.pigweb.eu/tna-calls>). Interested parties must register before an application can be submitted; template forms to prepare the submission are available via the PIGWEB project website.

B. Structure

The online submission and selection tool consists of different parts that will gradually become visible on the platform as the project progresses. The forms on which the tool is based are added to this deliverable as Annex B to Annex J. Guidelines to use the tool are available in the procedural manual and via the tool itself by means of short descriptions for the various parameters.

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1. Login

If you are new to the platform, you will first need to create a user account; if you already have a user account, you can log in with your username and password.

Principal Investigator Registry Form

If you have not registered yet, please do so by submitting required data through the form underneath. Following confirmation of your e-mail address you will be able to log in and access the project submission forms. If you already have an account, please log in to proceed.

First name

Last name

Phone number

E-mail

Organization name

Organization address

Organization Country

Password

Confirm password

[Save](#)

2. Homepage

An overview of the three calls within the PIGWEB project is given, together with the necessary links to the procedural manual and templates forms to prepare the submission.

Test Call
submissions stage 1 are open until August 30, 2021

First Call
Call for submissions opens on September 01, 2021

Second Call
Call for submissions opens on September 01, 2022

Third Call
Call for submissions opens on September 01, 2023

The transnational access (TNA) program of the PIGWEB project allows external teams (both academic and private researchers) to access the partners' infrastructures via submission of research proposals.

A budget of about 1.5 million euro is reserved to provide free access to top-quality pig research installations across Europe in an easy and transparent way.

For the first call, 28 [experimental pig research installations](#) are made available for TNA.

All guidelines regarding submission, selection, reporting and reimbursement can be consulted in the [procedural manual](#) and via the associated [template forms](#).

3. Submitting first stage application

All information about the TNA user and the TNA project (general, rationale, scientific quality and valorisation strategy) can be entered online.

information?projectId=1bd79d52

galletkoen@gmail.com Logout

GENERAL PARTICIPANTS RATIONALE SCIENTIFIC QUALITY VALORIZATION STRATEGY

Please do not enter any

Title

Short description

Preferred research installation

If applicable, please indicate the preferred research installation. An overview of all TNA installations can be found [here](#).

Preference 1

Preference 2

Preference 3

Is this application connected to another application in the current call of PIGWEB?

No

Yes

If yes, please provide the principal investigator's name and the project's title.

Principal investigator

Project title

Save

GENERAL PARTICIPANTS RATIONALE SCIENTIFIC QUALITY VALORIZATION STRATEGY

Participant(s)

First name	Last name	Phone	E-mail	Organization name	Organization address	Role
Virtual	User		virtual.user@whatever.com	ILVO	Burg. van Gansberghelaan 115, 9820 Merelbeke	Participant
Test	PI		galletkoen@gmail.com	ILVO	Burg. van Gansberghelaan 115, 9820 Merelbeke	ProjectLead

Additional participant

If applicable, please provide for each additional participant the same information as provided for the principal investigator.

First name

Last name

Phone

Email

Organization name

Organization address

Organization country

Save

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Please do not enter any personal or confidential data

Context

Describe the general context in which the project fits: outline the problem statement and indicate the relevance. Maximum 1500 characters, spaces included.

your text here ...

Objective(s)

Briefly state the overall objective(s) of your project. Maximum 500 characters, spaces included.

your text here...

Impact

Assess the expected impact of your project on sustainable pig production: describe the potential interest for the pig industry and the compliance with the European Green Deal. Maximum 1000 characters, spaces included.

your text here...

Save

Please do not enter any personal or confidential data

State of the art

Present the state of the art: describe the current knowledge and indicate the gaps. Maximum 1500 characters, spaces included.

your text here ...

Scientific question and hypothesis

Define a clear scientific question to which the project should provide an answer; formulate the appropriate hypothesis and describe the degree of innovation. Maximum 1500 characters, spaces included.

your text here ...

Approach

Briefly explain the approach to provide an answer to your scientific question: explain why the installation provided by PIGWEB offers added value and give an indication of the intended experimental design. Maximum 1000 characters, spaces included.

your text here ...

Save

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GENERAL PARTICIPANTS RATIONALE SCIENTIFIC QUALITY **VALORIZATION STRATEGY**

Please do not enter any personal or confidential data

valorization strategy
*Describe the intended valorization strategy: explain what the data will be used for (e.g. open data, scientific publication, patent or registration procedure).
Maximum 1000 characters, spaces included.*

your valorization strategy: -|

Save

4. Submitting second stage application
Tool page under construction
5. Evaluation of first/second stage applications
Tool page under construction.
6. Follow up of selection procedure
Tool page under construction.
7. Submitting start/interim/final reports
Tool page under construction.
8. Submitting follow-up questionnaire
Tool page under construction.
9. Submitting reimbursement claim
Tool page under construction.

IV. Conclusion

The procedural manual and the online submission and selection tool are crucial elements to guarantee an efficient and successful TNA process. Both will be updated as the project progresses and according to the users' needs. The TNA management team will be available for any suggestions or requests from the TNA users of TNA providers to make further improvements.

V. Annexes

- A. Procedural manual
- B. First stage application
- C. Second stage application
- D. First stage selection
- E. Second stage selection
- F. Start report
- G. Interim report
- H. Final report
- I. Follow-up questionnaire
- J. Reimbursement claim

PIGWEB

An infrastructure for experimental research for sustainable pig production

<https://www.pigweb.eu/>

The PIGWEB project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004770

PROCEDURAL MANUAL

Version 03 (July 2021)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction	3
2. Transnational access	3
3. Eligibility conditions	7
4. TNA process.....	7
5. Application procedure.....	8
5.1. First stage application.....	9
5.2. Second stage application	9
6. Selection procedure	9
6.1. First stage selection	9
6.2. Second stage selection	10
7. Reporting procedure	10
8. Valorization procedure.....	11
9. Reimbursement procedure	11
10. Support.....	12
11. Agreement.....	12
12. Forms.....	12
13. Data protection notice	13

1. INTRODUCTION

PIGWEB is a Horizon 2020 project that was launched on March 1, 2021. This five-year project gathers 16 different partners from nine different countries. The core aim of the project is to strengthen the pig research community by providing and facilitating access to research infrastructures, by reinforcing a culture of cooperation between the research community and industrial and societal stakeholders, and by improving and integrating the services provided by the research infrastructures. PIGWEB and all partners fully embrace the European Green Deal and the 'Farm to Fork' strategy to make Europe the world's first climate-neutral continent by 2050. Further detailed information about the project can be consulted on the project website <https://www.pigweb.eu/>.

2. TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS

The transnational access (TNA) programme of the PIGWEB project allows external teams (both academic and private researchers) to access the partners' infrastructures via submission of research proposals. A budget of about 1.5 million euro is reserved to provide free access to top-quality pig research installations across Europe in an easy and transparent way. In total, 28 experimental pig research installations of the 10 participating research infrastructures are made available for TNA (Figure 1, Table 1).

Figure 1 PIGWEB TNA consortium map. Ten research infrastructures (logos) in nine different countries (yellow) are offering TNA to 28 experimental pig research installations.

Table 1 PIGWEB TNA consortium partners.

Short name	Legal name	Country
Agroscope	Eidgenössische Departement für Wirtschaft, Bildung und Forschung	Switzerland
AU	Aarhus Universitet	Denmark
EV ILVO	Eigen Vermogen van het Instituut voor Landbouw- en Visserijonderzoek	Belgium
FBN	Institut für Nutztierbiologie	Germany
INRAE	Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement	France
IRTA	Institut de Recerca i Tecnologia Agroalimentaries	Spain
MATE	Hungarian University of Agricultural and Life Sciences	Hungary
Medicopus	Medicopus Egészségügyi Szolgáltató Közhasznú Nonprofit KFT	Hungary
SLU	Sveriges lantbruksuniversitet	Sweden
WU	Wageningen University	The Netherlands

The PIGWEB partners provide free access to a set of excellent experimental pig research installations, covering the most advanced technologies in the following research fields:

1. Do you want to assess **animal behaviour** to better understand and improve **animal welfare**? Five installations allow you to carry out different types of behavioural experiments (e.g., home pen behaviour such as maternal and suckling behaviour, or specific tests such as cognitive tasks and anxiety tests) using cameras and bioacoustics. Behaviour of pigs of different ages and of different breed and lines can be studied.
2. Do you want to know more about **body and carcass composition**? Five installations give you the possibility to study the effect of experimental treatments on nutrient and energy deposition rate or efficiency in live pigs or nutrient and energy content of the carcasses, by using either dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DXA), computed tomography (CT) or by grinding and analysing the animals.
3. Are you interested in **calorimetry**? Three installations offer the possibility to measure effects of experimental treatments on heat production measured by gaseous exchange (i.e., O₂ consumption and CO₂ production) under a wide variety of highly controlled

environmental and housing conditions. These measurements can be part of a complete energy and nitrogen balance study, and/or can be combined with the measurement of metabolites, or emissions of other gases or feeding behaviour and physical activity characterization.

4. Do you want to quantify **emissions** to study the environmental impact of pig production? Four installations allow you to measure gas emissions (e.g., CH₄, NH₃, and/or N₂O) and odours in controlled experimental barns, in respiration chambers, or in *in vitro* systems.
5. Do you want to produce an experimental **feed**? Three feed manufacturing installations are made available where high-precision **feed technologies** can be applied under well-controlled and traceable conditions to process feed ingredients into complete feeds that meet the requirements of precision nutrition research.
6. Are you focussing on **metabolism and physiology**? Eleven installations offer you the possibility to assess nutrient transformation and feed efficiency of pigs, and the environmental impact of variable production conditions.
7. Do you want to study specific elements of pig **production systems**? Six installations allow you to perform various experiments with different feeding strategies, different breeds or different systems (e.g., conventional or organic systems or loose-housed sows during farrowing). The modern and flexible installations provide data recording of body weight, feed intake and/or water consumption. Depending on the installation, registrations can be done both at an individual level and/or at group level at different stages from birth to slaughter.

An overview of the main expertise offered for TNA by each organisation is given in Table 2. A detailed description of all research installations is available on the project website.

Support from the PIGWEB budget varies among installations, but covers in general the operating costs of the installations, all experiment-associated costs (e.g., animal care, feeding, monitoring, sampling, sample preparation, lab analysis, and data analysis) as described by the TNA provider and the costs for travel and subsistence if participation is required.

Each research installation has a budget based on a 'unit of access', i.e., ton.feed.week, pig.week, pork.week, or lab.week. One ton.feed.week corresponds to the production of one ton of feed in one week (considering the time required for preparation, fabrication, and analyses). Likewise, one pig.week corresponds to housing a pig in an installation for one week and carrying out the measurements proposed by the installation. One pork.week corresponds to the scanning and/or slaughter of one pig, while one lab.week corresponds to the number of samples that can be analysed in one week. An overview of the available units of access per installation can be found on the website. It is possible to ask for a study that exceeds the available pig.weeks, feed.weeks, lab.weeks or pork.weeks at a particular installation if it remains feasible for the installation and if the applicant pays for the extra costs.

Table 2 Main expertise offered for TNA.

Organization	Installation	Animal behaviour and welfare	Body and carcass composition	Calorimetry	Emissions	Feed and feed technologies	Metabolism and physiology	Production systems
Agroscope	DXA							
	Metabolism							
AU	Piglets							
	Feed							
	Lactation							
EV ILVO	Gestation							
	Nursery							
	Emissions & odours							
	Nutrient balance							
FBN	PigHouse							
	ExpPhysioRo							
	EnergyLab							
	BehaveLab							
	GenSuite							
INRAE	Feed mill							
	Calorimetry							
	PLF							
	RFI lines							
	Creole breed							
IRTA	Feed mill and laboratory							
	Abattoir and CT unit							
MATE	Perform							
	Rapid analysis							
	Lipid-mycotoxin							
Medicopus	CT lab							
SLU	Lövsta							
WU	Respirometry unit							
	Behavioural research unit							

3. ELIGIBILITY CONDITIONS

The TNA programme is open to researchers in academia and industry from any country, although priority (at least 80% of all funded access) will be given to organizations legally established within an EU Member or Associated State¹. The TNA applicant cannot be a partner of the PIGWEB project and has to be established in a country other than the country of the requested infrastructure. The country in which the applicant is working is considered rather than the applicant's nationality. A schematic overview of who is eligible for TNA is given by the decision tree in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Decision tree for TNA eligibility.

4. TNA PROCESS

The entire TNA process is based on a continuous collaboration between and the TNA applicant, the TNA provider, and the TNA management team (Figure 3). To ensure a successful outcome, all parties must strictly comply with the prescribed procedures concerning application, selection, reporting, and valorisation. In the different sections below (section 5-9), these procedures are explained in more detail.

The start of the TNA project is defined as the day the first unit of access starts; the end of the TNA project is defined as the day the last unit of access ends.

¹ Associated states: Switzerland, Norway, Iceland and Liechtenstein, Israel, Turkey, Croatia, the Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia and Serbia, Albania and Montenegro, Bosnia & Herzegovina

Figure 3 Roadmap for TNA. Key tasks to be performed by the TNA applicant (green), the TNA provider (blue), or the TNA management team (pink).

5. APPLICATION PROCEDURE

A two-stage application process is used for each of the three calls envisaged over the course of the PIGWEB project (March 2021 – February 2026). The first call will be launched in September 2021, the second call by September 2022 and the third (last) call by September 2023. Each call will remain open for 3 months for first-stage proposals. For the first stage, a general pre-proposal is expected, whereas for the second stage application, a detailed full proposal should be submitted. The deadlines for submission of the applications are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Application submission deadlines.

Call	First stage application deadline	Second stage application deadline
September 1, 2021	December 1, 2021	March 31, 2022
September 1, 2022	December 1, 2022*	March 31, 2023*
September 1, 2023	December 1, 2023*	March 31, 2024*

*Provisional deadline, might change during the course of the project

Applications for TNA should be made in accordance with the guidelines given below and should be submitted using the online TNA tool available on the project website. Guidance for submission is available within the application forms and through this manual. First-time users and users who would normally not have access to specific installations in their own country are encouraged to apply.

5.1. First stage application

Applicants are requested to submit a pre-proposal, mainly providing information about:

- The rationale: describe the context in which the project fits, indicate the overall objective and assess the expected impact on sustainable pig production.
- The scientific quality: present the state of the art, define a clear scientific question to which the project should provide an answer, formulate the appropriate hypothesis and briefly explain the approach to be followed.
- The valorisation strategy: explain what the data will be used for (e.g. open data, scientific publication, patent or registration procedure).

5.2. Second stage application

Selected pre-proposals will be invited to submit a full proposal, which should be prepared in close collaboration with the TNA provider. Full applications should provide information about:

- The scientific and ethical soundness: resume the final scientific question, describe the design of the trial, including e.g. details related to the number of animals, the number of treatments, the response traits, the number of replicates and the experimental unit, demonstrate a responsible use of experimental animals and give the anticipated timetable.
- The practical and financial feasibility, including e.g. the number of units of access, necessary approvals from the ethical committee or other authorities, information on visits and/or participation by the applicant, and an overview of potential risks.

All work must comply with the European Union legislation on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes (Directive 2010/63/EU), as well as any national requirements in the country where the work will be conducted. If participation by the TNA applicant is required during the experiment, it should be ensured that the person participating has the appropriate training and licenses.

6. SELECTION PROCEDURE

Applications will be reviewed by the User Selection Panel, which is composed of three internal and three external experts from the PIGWEB consortium. The TNA applicant will be able to follow the selection process through the online TNA tool. For unsuccessful applications, feedback, suggestions for improvement and options for resubmission will be available on request. Applications that are not approved can be resubmitted at a subsequent call.

6.1. First stage selection

Proposals will be assessed by the User Selection Panel on the rationale (40/100), scientific quality (40/100), and valorisation strategy (20/100). The main criteria in the first stage selection round are therefore the relevance, possible impact, scientific questioning, degree of innovation, and valorisation potential. A threshold of 28/40 for both the rationale and the

scientific quality, and of 16/20 for the valorisation strategy will be used. Applications with lower scores will not be considered. Applications with higher scores will be retained for selection, which will be based on the total score and the available budget. Applicants will be notified of the outcome of the first stage selection within four weeks after closing the call (Figure 4).

6.2. Second stage selection

The main criteria in the second stage selection round are the scientific and ethical soundness of the proposal, together with the practical and financial feasibility. A threshold of 70/100 for the scientific soundness will be used. Applications with lower scores will not be considered. Applications with higher scores will be retained for selection, which will be based on the total score and the available budget. In addition, the User Selection Panel will assess the responsible use of experimental animals and the TNA provider must attest the feasibility of the proposed work.

Applicants will be notified of the outcome of the second stage selection process within eight weeks after the second stage application submission deadline (Figure 4). Provisional approval will be granted pending possible approval by other authorities (e.g., derogation or ethical committee). In the event of a positive outcome, TNA applicants need to contact the TNA provider to apply for this additional approval. Without the approval of authorisation bodies, the experiment will not be able to start. Official documents regarding the approval by the ethical committee must be delivered to the TNA Management team.

Figure 4 TNA application and selection timeline.

7. REPORTING PROCEDURE

To monitor and guide the TNA projects, TNA users are expected to deliver concise reports at the start, mid-way, and upon termination of the TNA project. Reports should be submitted using the online TNA tool available on the project website and approved by the TNA provider. In addition, to further improve the TNA programme, a mandatory follow-up questionnaire will be sent to all TNA users. This questionnaire is expected to be submitted together with the final

report. Guidance for submission is available within the report forms. The deadlines for reporting are presented in Table 4.

Table 4 Reporting deadlines.

Start report deadline	one week after start of the TNA project
Interim report deadline	halfway TNA project
Final report deadline	four months after termination of the TNA project

8. VALORIZATION PROCEDURE

TNA users have the rights to the data obtained, but they are expected to valorise their results as soon as feasible (pending protection of intellectual property), preferably in Open Access publications. Authors are also encouraged to make the raw data accessible in repositories using the FAIR data principles². Co-authorship is required when there is a significant contribution by the TNA provider in the trial design or processing of the data. In case the data will not be published in a scientific paper, another valorisation-strategy is expected (e.g., patent or registration procedure). Details of the valorisation plans must be clearly explained in the first stage application.

In each publication and communication resulting from a TNA project, it is mandatory to specify that the project received research funding from the European Community's Horizon 2020 Program, by using the acknowledgement sentence: 'This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004770'. In addition, the host organization and, if applicable, research funding supporting the specific infrastructure must be acknowledged.

9. REIMBURSEMENT PROCEDURE

When visiting the research infrastructure, PIGWEB can subsidize travel and subsistence costs. Either the TNA user or the TNA provider (upon agreement) can make the bookings. It is expected to choose the most cost-effective form(s) of travel and accommodation. In case the TNA user makes the bookings, the TNA provider must be contacted to discuss the travel budget. Costs that exceed the agreed travel budget cannot be reimbursed. In addition, without submission of the final report, including the follow-up questionnaire, costs cannot be reimbursed.

Boarding passes, travel agency invoices, original tickets or e-tickets must be submitted along the reimbursement claim form. For reimbursement of travel expenses incurred in a currency other than Euro, conversion will be made using the official ECB exchange rate on the date of

² Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* **3**, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

the expense. The cost of a journey by private car (user's personal or company car) is calculated at a rate per km in accordance with the internal rules of the TNA provider concerned. Fuel is included in the kilometer rate. Road tolls may be paid extra. When two or more participants travel together by car, travel costs will be reimbursed to only one person. The total cost of travel by car cannot exceed the maximum cost of an equivalent flight. Car rental costs cannot be covered unless it is the more convenient way to travel. Car insurance costs cannot be covered.

10. SUPPORT

PIGWEB created an Access Management Team as a main contact point and supporting body for potential TNA users. Its aim is to advise potential users on the most suitable research facilities, to assist in the submission of applications and to answer any further questions about the TNA programme. This team is composed of Jaap van Milgen (jaap.vanmilgen@inrae.fr, INRAE, coordinator of PIGWEB), Carolien De Cuyper (carolien.decuyper@ilvo.vlaanderen.be, EV ILVO, responsible person for TNA), Cornelia Metges (metges@fhn-dummerstorf.de, FHN, member of the user selection panel) and Sam Millet (sam.millet@ilvo.vlaanderen.be, EV ILVO, TNA work package leader). Potential TNA users have the possibility to contact this team via their email address or via the project website. In addition, a FAQ page is available on the project website, providing an answer to the most frequently asked questions.

11. AGREEMENT

It is strongly recommended to have an agreement between the TNA provider and the TNA user, including all details regarding e.g.:

- what's included in the unit of access
- the maximum travel and subsistence budget
- the data transfer
- the intended valorisation strategy

12. FORMS

All forms for application, reporting and travel reimbursement are available via the online TNA tool at the project website:

- First stage application
- Second stage application
- Start report
- Interim report
- Final report
- Follow-up questionnaire

- Reimbursement claim

13. DATA PROTECTION NOTICE

1. PIGWEB is a consortium made of several institutions that are supported by the EU Horizon 2020 Framework Program to conduct a 5-years' research project under the coordination of the Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement (**INRAE**), a French public research institute dedicated to agricultural science.
2. The Own Capital fund of ILVO (Eigen Vermogen van het Instituut voor Landbouw- en Visserijonderzoek; **EV ILVO**), with registered office at Burgemeester Van Gansberghelaan 92/1, 9820 Merelbeke, Belgium, is an independent scientific research institute, which aims to improve the knowledge and the dissemination of research results on the sustainability of agriculture, fisheries and agri-food sector. Based on the description of PIGWEB activities included in Grant Agreement No 101004770, Annex 1, EV ILVO is authorized by the PIGWEB Consortium to develop and update the Transnational Access (**TNA**) portal, namely a web-based interface for launching a transnational call for proposals and possibly offering other services.
3. For the purposes of its activities within the TNA portal, EV ILVO may need to process certain personal data or personal information concerning individuals who apply to the TNA funding and services that could be made available by the PIGWEB consortium.
4. For the purpose of this Data Protection Notice and pursuant to Article 4 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), "personal data" means "any information relating to a natural person identified or identifiable, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person"; "processing" means "any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organization, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction".
5. Your personal data will/may be processed by EV ILVO on behalf of the PIGWEB Consortium for the following purposes:
 - a. Processing applications to the PIGWEB TNA call for proposals;
 - b. Administering and/or managing applicants' communications with the TNA portal administrators and particularly with the TNA Access Point (including mailing of correspondence, statements or notices to applicants);
 - c. Managing activities related to the implementation, monitoring and evaluation of TNA research projects;
 - d. Responding to any enquiries by applicants;
 - e. Implementing other activities related to PIGWEB objectives.
6. Unless consent is revoked, EV ILVO, on behalf of the PIGWEB Consortium, will store your personal data for as long as it is necessary for the purpose(s) as described. The PIGWEB

consortium represented by the project coordinator Jaap van Milgen, INRAE, and EV ILVO, represented by the TNA contact persons Sam Millet and Carolien De Cuyper, lawfully and rightfully process personal data in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679. Personal data are processed by EV ILVO on behalf of the PIGWEB consortium in a manner that ensures appropriate security, including protection against unauthorized or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organizational measures, and kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than it is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed.

7. The processing of personal data by the PIGWEB Consortium and EV ILVO shall be without prejudice to all the rights conferred to you as data subject by Articles 15-21 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679, namely:
 - a. Right to have **access** to your own personal data processed by the PIGWEB Consortium and to receive the information on the persons or third parties who have directly or indirectly access to your personal data stored in the EV ILVO databases; this include the right to receive a response to the request for the information whether your personal data are being processed and receive the personal data within 30 calendar days after the request is made;³
 - b. Right to obtain the **rectification** without undue delay of inaccurate or incomplete personal data;
 - c. Right to obtain the **restriction of processing** of your personal data where they are: (a) inaccurate; (b) no longer necessary in relation to the purposes for which they were processed, but you need them for the establishment, exercise or defense of your legal claims;
 - d. Right to obtain the **erasure** without undue delay of your personal data where: (a) they are no longer necessary in relation to the purposes for which they were processed; (b) they have been unlawfully processed; c) you have exercised your right of withdrawal of consent on which the processing is based and there is no other legal ground for the processing;
 - e. Right to require the provision of your personal data in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format; and where technically feasible, to transmit your data directly to another controller of your choice (right to **data portability**);
 - f. Right to **object** at any time to processing of personal data where they are processed for direct marketing purposes, which includes profiling to the extent that it is related to such direct marketing;
 - g. Right to **protect** your personal data from unlawful processing or accidental loss, destruction or damage caused by intentional or untimely concealment, and the right for protection from information which is unreliable or harms the person's honor, dignity, and business reputation;
 - h. Right to **lodge a complaint** with the supervisory authority to safeguard your rights of personal data protection;
 - i. Right to **withdraw your consent** to processing your personal data at any time.

³ That period may be extended by two further months where necessary, taking into account the complexity and number of the requests. EV ILVO shall inform the data subject of any such extension within one month of receipt of the request, together with the reasons for the delay (Article 12(3) GDPR).

8. In relation to data transfer outside the EEA (European Economic Area), within the PIGWEB Consortium or within PIGWEB TNA call, no personal data will be transferred to/from non EU countries.

Accomplishment of all rights can be demanded by contacting the EV ILVO's data protection officer, Bart Ampe, by email (privacy@ilvo.vlaanderen.be).

This Data Protection Notice serves as an integral part of the terms and conditions of all TNA portal activities developed by the PIGWEB consortium.

PIGWEB

An infrastructure for experimental research for sustainable pig production

<https://www.pigweb.eu/>

The PIGWEB project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004770

FIRST STAGE APPLICATION

Version 02 (July 2021)

1. TNA USER INFORMATION

Principal investigator

Please provide the following information for the principal investigator.

First name

Last name

Phone

E-mail

Organization name

Organization address

Additional participants

If applicable, please provide for each additional participant the same information requested for the principal investigator.

First name

Last name

Phone

E-mail

Organization name

Organization address

2. TNA PROJECT INFORMATION

Is this application connected to another application in the current call of PIGWEB?

If yes, please describe how the applications are related.

- No
- Yes

Principal investigator

Project title

Relation

Please do not enter any personal or confidential data from this point on as the next part will be sent to the reviewers for evaluation.

Project title

Research installation

If applicable, please indicate your first, second and third preference of research installation.

Preference 1

Choose an installation

Preference 2

Choose an installation

Preference 3

Choose an installation

2.1 RATIONALE

Context

Describe the general context in which the project fits: outline the problem statement and indicate the relevance. Maximum 1500 characters, spaces included.

Click to add text

Objective

Briefly state the overall objective of your project. Maximum 500 characters, spaces included.

Click to add text

Impact

Assess the expected impact of your project on sustainable pig production: describe the potential interest for the pig industry and the compliance with the European Green Deal. Maximum 1000 characters, spaces included.

Click to add text

2.2 SCIENTIFIC QUALITY

State of the art

Present the state of the art: describe the current knowledge and indicate the gaps. Maximum 1500 characters, spaces included.

Click to add text

Scientific question and hypothesis

Define a clear scientific question to which the project should provide an answer; formulate the appropriate hypothesis and describe the degree of innovation. Maximum 1500 characters, spaces included.

Click to add text

Approach

Briefly explain the approach to provide an answer to your scientific question: explain why the installation provided by PIGWEB offers added value and give an indication of the intended experimental design. Maximum 1000 characters, spaces included.

Click to add text

2.3 VALORISATION STRATEGY

Describe the intended valorisation strategy: explain what the data will be used for (e.g. open data, scientific publication, patent or registration procedure). Maximum 1000 characters, spaces included.

Click to add text

On website:

We have received your submission.

Please check your inbox for a confirmation email.

Your application will be evaluated by the User Selection Panel.

You will be informed about the selection outcome by December 29.

Successful pre-proposals will receive further instructions on how to proceed.

Thank you for your interest in PIGWEB.

PIGWEB

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SECOND STAGE APPLICATION

Version 02 (July 2021)

1. TNA USER INFORMATION

Principal investigator

Please provide the following information for the principal investigator.

First name	Click to add text
Last name	Click to add text
Phone	Click to add text
E-mail	Click to add text
Organization name	Click to add text
Organization address	Click to add text

Additional participants

If applicable, please provide for each additional participant the same information requested for the principal investigator.

First name	Click to add text
Last name	Click to add text
Phone	Click to add text
E-mail	Click to add text
Organization name	Click to add text
Organization address	Click to add text

2. TNA PROJECT INFORMATION

Project title

Research installation

Please do not enter any personal or confidential data from this point on as the next part will be sent to the reviewers for evaluation.

2.1 SCIENTIFIC AND ETHICAL SOUNDNESS

Scientific question

Resume the final scientific question to which the project should provide an answer. Maximum 1500 characters, spaces included.

Trial design

Describe the design of the trial: provide a complete and structured description of the entire experimental setup, including e.g. all details related to the number of animals, the number of treatments, the response traits, the number of replicates, the experimental unit. Maximum 5000 characters, spaces included.

Click to add text

Responsible use of experimental animals

Justify the number of animals needed and indicate how you addressed the '3Rs' principle (Replacement, Reduction and Refinement). Maximum 2000 characters, spaces included.

Click to add text

Timetable

Give the anticipated timetable of the trial, including an indication of when all data and analyses will be available and the TNA project will be finalized. Maximum 500 characters, spaces included.

Click to add text

Do you confirm to comply with the intended valorisation strategy described in the first stage application? If yes, please copy the strategy; if not, please explain and give an update.

Yes

Click to add text

No

Click to add text

2.2 PRACTICAL AND FINANCIAL FEASIBILITY

Number of units of access

	Yes	No
Is an approval from the local ethical committee required?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Is any other approval required? If yes, specify. <input type="text" value="Click to add text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Will you visit the installation?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If yes, is there an agreement on the maximum costs for travel and subsistence?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Will you participate in the trial?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If yes, do all persons participating have the appropriate training and license?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Do you agree to self-finance additional costs in case you opt for e.g. extra units of access, extra analyses not covered by the unit of access or extra visits?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Risks

Describe the potential risks (e.g. African swine fever, COVID-19 or delivery of products) that might occur and indicate how you plan to avoid, mitigate or resolve them. Maximum 1000 characters, spaces included.

Click to add text

On website:

We have received your submission.

Please check your inbox for a confirmation email.

Your application will be evaluated by the User Selection Panel.

You will be informed about the selection outcome by May 26.

Successful proposals will receive further instructions on how to proceed.

Thank you for your interest in PIGWEB.

On website:

Approval by the TNA provider

The TNA provider declares the trial practical and financial feasible.

PIGWEB

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FIRST STAGE SELECTION

Version 02 (July 2021)

Project title

Please copy the project title as mentioned on the first stage application form.

Click to add text

Project reference number

Please copy the project reference number.

Click to add text

User Selection Panel member

Please select the appropriate member of the User Selection Panel reviewing this application.

Select a member

Review

First stage applications are assessed on the rationale, the scientific quality and the valorisation strategy. Please use the proposed scoring system¹ and briefly describe the reason for your evaluation. Applications with scores lower than the threshold scores will not be considered; applications with higher scores will be retained for selection.

1. RATIONALE (40% total points)

The rationale includes the context in which the project fits, the main objectives and the expected impact on sustainable pig production.

Score	Maximum	Threshold
Click to add score	100	70

Reason for your evaluation

Briefly explain why this score was given (maximum 150 words).

Click to add text

2. SCIENTIFIC QUALITY (40% total points)

The scientific quality includes the state of the art, the scientific question to answer, the hypothesis and the intended approach.

Score	Maximum	Threshold
Click to add score	100	70

Reason for your evaluation

Briefly explain why this score was given (maximum 150 words).

Click to add text

3. VALORISATION STRATEGY (20% total points)

The valorisation strategy describes what the data will be used for e.g. open data, scientific publication, patent or registration procedure.

Score	Maximum	Threshold
-------	---------	-----------

¹ [0-50] unacceptable, [50-60] weak, [60-70] satisfactory, [70-80] good, [80-90] very good, [90-100] excellent

Click to add score	100	80
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Reason for your evaluation

Briefly explain why this score was given (maximum 150 words).

Click to add text

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SECOND STAGE SELECTION

Version 02 (July 2021)

Project title

Please copy the project title as mentioned on the second stage application form.

Click to add text

Project reference number

Please copy the project reference number.

Click to add text

User Selection Panel member

Please select the appropriate member of the User Selection Panel reviewing this application.

Select a member

Review

Second stage applications are assessed on the scientific and ethical soundness, along with the practical and financial feasibility. For the scientific soundness, please use the proposed scoring system¹ and briefly describe the reason for your evaluation. Applications with scores lower than the threshold score will not be considered; applications with higher scores will be retained for selection. For ethical soundness and feasibility, please select yes/no and briefly describe the reason for your evaluation. Applications with a negative feedback will not be considered; applications with a positive feedback will be retained for selection.

1. SCIENTIFIC SOUNDNESS

The scientific soundness includes the scientific question, the trial design and the valorisation strategy.

Score	Maximum	Threshold
Click to add score	100	70

Reason for your evaluation

Briefly explain why this score was given (maximum 150 words).

Click to add text

2. ETHICAL SOUNDNESS

The ethical soundness includes the responsible use of experimental animals.

In your opinion, does this proposal needs approval from an ethical committee? Yes No
In your opinion, are the research strategy and the methods ethically sound? Yes No

Reason for your evaluation

Briefly explain why this score was given (maximum 150 words).

Click to add text

3. PRACTICAL AND FINANCIAL FEASIBILITY

Since the proposal has to be written with the TNA provider, the TNA provider has to ensure the feasibility of the proposed work.

¹ [0-50] unacceptable, [50-60] weak, [60-70] satisfactory, [70-80] good, [80-90] very good, [90-100] excellent

Does the TNA provider declares the trial practical and financial feasible? Yes No

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START REPORT

Version 02 (July 2021)

1. TNA USER INFORMATION

Principal investigator

Please provide the following information for the principal investigator.

First name	Click to add text
Last name	Click to add text
Phone	Click to add text
E-mail	Click to add text
Organization name	Click to add text
Organization address	Click to add text

Additional participants

If applicable, please provide for each additional participant the same information requested for the principal investigator.

First name	Click to add text
Last name	Click to add text
Phone	Click to add text
E-mail	Click to add text
Organization name	Click to add text
Organization address	Click to add text

2. TNA PROJECT INFORMATION

Project title

Research installation

TNA provider

Please provide the following information for the TNA provider.

First name	Click to add text
Last name	Click to add text
Phone	Click to add text
E-mail	Click to add text

Agreement

Is there a written agreement between the TNA user and the TNA provider about the TNA project, including what data, when and how it should be provided to the TNA user?

- Yes
 No
-

Approvals

	Yes	No
Was approval by the local ethical committee required?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If yes, was the trial approved?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If yes, was the approval sent to the TNA Management team?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Was there any other approval required?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If yes, please specify. Click to add text		
If yes, was the trial approved?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Timetable

Start date of the TNA project <i>I.e. the day the first unit of access starts</i>	Click to select a date
End date of the TNA project <i>I.e. the day the last unit of access ends</i>	Click to select a date
Expected date interim report <i>Interim reports should be submitted halfway the TNA project</i>	Click to select a date
Expected date final report <i>Final reports should be submitted at the latest four months after termination of the TNA project</i>	Click to select a date

Resources

Number of units of access	Click to add text
Travel and subsistence budget	Click to add text

Final trial design

Describe the final design of the trial, as approved by the TNA provider. Maximum 5000 characters, spaces included.

[Click to add text](#)

Remarks

If you have any comments about the TNA process, please feel free to share them.

[Click to add text](#)

On website:

Approved by the TNA provider

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INTERIM REPORT

Version 02 (July 2021)

1. TNA USER INFORMATION

Principal investigator

Please provide the following information for the principal investigator.

First name	Click to add text
Last name	Click to add text
Phone	Click to add text
E-mail	Click to add text
Organization name	Click to add text
Organization address	Click to add text

Additional participants

If applicable, please provide for each additional participant the same information requested for the principal investigator.

First name	Click to add text
Last name	Click to add text
Phone	Click to add text
E-mail	Click to add text
Organization name	Click to add text
Organization address	Click to add text

2. TNA PROJECT INFORMATION

Project title

Research installation

TNA provider

Please provide the following information for the TNA provider.

First name	Click to add text
Last name	Click to add text
Phone	Click to add text
E-mail	Click to add text

Course of the trial

Does the number of units of access still apply?

Yes**No**

Does the agreed budget for travel and subsistence still apply?

Does the final trial design still apply?

Does the anticipated timetable still apply?

If No, please explain and describe the impact on the TNA project.

[Click to add text](#)

Remarks

If you have any comments about the TNA process, please feel free to share them.

[Click to add text](#)

On website:

Approved by the TNA provider

PIGWEB

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FINAL REPORT

Version 02 (July 2021)

1. TNA USER INFORMATION

Principal investigator

Please provide the following information for the principal investigator.

First name	Click to add text
Last name	Click to add text
Phone	Click to add text
E-mail	Click to add text
Organization name	Click to add text
Organization address	Click to add text

Additional participants

If applicable, please provide for each additional participant the same information requested for the principal investigator.

First name	Click to add text
Last name	Click to add text
Phone	Click to add text
E-mail	Click to add text
Organization name	Click to add text
Organization address	Click to add text

2. TNA PROJECT INFORMATION

Project title

Research installation

TNA provider

Please provide the following information for the TNA provider.

First name	Click to add text
Last name	Click to add text
Phone	Click to add text
E-mail	Click to add text

Timetable

Start date of the TNA project

I.e. the date the first unit of access started

Click to select a date

End date of the TNA project

I.e. the date the last unit of access ends

Click to select a date

Course of the trial

Did unexpected events occur during the course of the project?

Yes

No

If Yes, please explain and describe the impact on the TNA project.

Click to add text

Results

Describe the rationale, the scientific questioning, the hypothesis, the approach and main outcomes of the project. Maximum 5000 characters, spaces included.

Click to add text

Valorisation strategy

Indicate which steps you will take to implement the intended valorization strategy. Max. 1000 characters, spaces included.

Click to add text

Remarks

If you have any comments about the TNA process, please feel free to share them.

Click to add text

On website:

Approved by the TNA provider

PIGWEB

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FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONNAIRE

Version 02 (July 2021)

1. TNA USER INFORMATION

Principal investigator

Please provide the following information for the principal investigator.

First name	Click to add text
Last name	Click to add text
Phone	Click to add text
E-mail	Click to add text
Organization name	Click to add text
Organization address	Click to add text

Additional participants

If applicable, please provide for each additional participant the same information requested for the principal investigator.

First name	Click to add text
Last name	Click to add text
Phone	Click to add text
E-mail	Click to add text
Organization name	Click to add text
Organization address	Click to add text

2. TNA PROJECT INFORMATION

Project title Click to add text

Research installation

Select the assigned installation

Reference number

Please provide the reference number received with the first stage application.

Click to add text

How did you find out about the PIGWEB project and the possibility to apply for TNA?

- Twitter
- LinkedIn
- Facebook

- ResearchGate
 - Colleagues
 - Other: [Click to add text](#)
-

Was there enough information provided by the following documents?

	Yes	No
▪ TNA overview	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
▪ Procedural manual	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
▪ Online submission and selection tool guide	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If No, please explain.

[Click to add text](#)

Was it clear to fill in the following forms?

	Yes	No
▪ First stage application	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
▪ Second stage application	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
▪ Start report	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
▪ Interim report	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
▪ Final report	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
▪ Reimbursement form	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
▪ Follow-up questionnaire	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If No, please explain.

[Click to add text](#)

How did you experience the exchange with the infrastructure before submitting the full proposal?

[Click to add text](#)

How did you experience the exchange with the infrastructure during the TNA project?

[Click to add text](#)

How did you experience the exchange with the infrastructure after the TNA project?

[Click to add text](#)

Did you have a written agreement with the TNA provider, besides the experimental protocol?

- Yes
 - No
-

Was all data exchanged as agreed?

Yes

No

If No, please explain.

[Click to add text](#)

Did you have a meeting at the end of the TNA project for evaluation?

Yes

No

From start to end: what were the most difficult issues to deal with?

[Click to add text](#)

Do you have any suggestions for improvement of the TNA process?

Yes

No

If Yes, please specify.

[Click to add text](#)
